

Neural Implicit Swept Volume Models for Fast Collision Detection

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Abstract—Collision detection is one of the most time-consuming operations during motion planning. Thus, there is an increasing interest in exploring machine learning techniques to speed up collision detection and sampling-based motion planning. A recent line of research focuses on utilizing neural signed distance functions of either the robot geometry or the swept volume of the robot motion. Building on this, we present a novel neural implicit swept volume model to continuously represent arbitrary motions parameterized by their start and goal configurations. This allows to quickly compute signed distances for any point in the task space to the robot motion. Further, we present an algorithm combining the speed of the deep learning-based signed distance computations with the strong accuracy guarantees of geometric collision checkers. We validate our approach in simulated and real-world robotic experiments, and demonstrate that it is able to speed up a commercial bin picking application.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bin picking is a crucial task in logistics and industrial automation processes. Solving this task typically involves several steps, such as object localization, grasp pose selection, and collision-free motion planning [1], [2]. There exist multiple paradigms for finding a collision-free path: for example, one can use a path planner (sampling-based or optimization-based) to construct a single collision-free path. In practice, bin picking applications often follow a different paradigm where a set of paths is first heuristically generated and subsequently checked for collisions until a first collision-free path has been found.

Besides object detection, these collision checks are one of the most time-consuming steps in bin picking applications. Geometric collision detection methods typically discretize the motion along a path into small-enough steps and check the resulting robot configurations against the environment [3], [4]. In this paper, we follow a different approach utilizing the so-called swept volume of a robot motion, which is the subset of the workspace that the robot moves through during this motion. An explicit representation of this volume would allow to replace the individual collision checks along a path segment with a single collision check of this swept volume against the environment.

However, computing an *explicit* representation of the swept volume comes with its own drawbacks. It is usually done via voxel grid approximations, or by geometrically approximating the boundary of this volume, e.g., as a triangle mesh [5]. By design the accuracy of these approaches is

Fig. 1: The basic idea of our approach is to predict the signed distance (black line) of a point in the task space (black dot) to its nearest point (white dot) on the surface of the swept volume (blue mesh) of a robot motion. The swept volume is implicitly represented by a neural network, which takes the start and goal configuration of the motion as well as the query point as inputs and outputs the signed distance of the point to the implied swept volume. The robot motion can be collision checked against a complete environment, by representing the environment as a point cloud. Each of these points becomes one input point for the network.

strongly linked to their computation time, which hinders their application for collision checking in live systems.

We thus propose an *implicit* representation based on a deep neural network that learns the function $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{q}_1) \mapsto \delta$, where \mathbf{q}_0 is the start configuration of the robot, \mathbf{q}_1 is the goal configuration, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the query point in the task space for which we want to perform a collision check, and δ is the signed distance of the query point to the resulting swept volume when performing the motion $\mathbf{q}_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{q}_1$, see also Fig. 1. This approach learns a continuous implicit swept volume model, i.e., it can predict a signed distance for any point in the task space, and is not limited to a fixed resolution of a voxel grid. Further, for a given network the inference time is independent of the length of the motion.

This approach can be used to check a robot motion against a complete environment represented as a point cloud. Each point \mathbf{x} of this point cloud becomes one input for the network. Multiple points can be batch processed leveraging parallel computation on GPUs, which allows for favorable computation times compared to geometric collision checkers (GCC). However, a downside of this approach is that the distance computed by a neural network is less reliable when compared to a GCC. Neural networks cannot be guaranteed to extrapolate robustly to data not seen during training [6], [7], [8]. This hinders applications in industrial settings, as trading off accuracy against speed is not acceptable when it comes to safety and potential collisions.

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We therefore propose an algorithm that interleaves our implicit swept volume model with a GCC. As we will show in our experiments, this effectively reduces the number of paths that have to be checked by the GCC and thus also reduces the total time spent to find a collision-free path, even when considering the additional time spent on computing the swept volume distances.

While our primary example revolves around a bin picking application, it is worth noting that the same model is also suitable for collision checks in general sampling-based motion planners. Moreover, while our evaluation focuses on a robotic arm, our approach can be broadly applied to any articulated object that allows for swept volume computation.

The main contributions of this paper are: (a) a novel approach to modeling robot motions as implicit swept volumes parameterized by the start and goal configuration with a neural network, and (b) an algorithm that utilizes these neural swept volumes to speed up collision checking while preserving accuracy guarantees of GCCs.

II. RELATED WORK

Chiang et al. [9] proposed a neural network that learned to map the start and goal configuration of a robot motion to the swept volume (as a scalar value) of this motion. The motion is assumed to be linear in joint space. This is not usable for collision detection, but has been used as a heuristic to speed up a sampling-based motion planner. Building on this, Baxter et al. [10] proposed a network that uses the same input, but outputs a voxel grid representation of the swept volume (voxels can either be “swept” or “not swept”). This method can be used for collision checks, but on the downside it has an inherent discretization error determined by the size of the voxel grid cells, and a low spatial resolution due to the limited number of voxels. In contrast, in a feasibility study Lee et al. [11] used the deep signed distance model of Gropp et al. [12] to model swept volumes implicitly as a signed distance field (SDF), thereby avoiding discretizations. However, their model is not conditioned on motion parameters, but directly maps a point in the task space to the signed distance of an implicit swept volume. Thus, each trained network represents the swept volume of only one specific motion. Michaux et al. [13] learn a parameterized signed distance function of zonotope approximations of a box obstacle and a swept volume of a robot motion. The inputs of their network are the box obstacle center, as well as the initial configuration, speed, and acceleration of the robot, which uniquely determines the motion of a robot. They use this SDF as a collision avoidance constraint in receding time horizon planning.

Besides modeling swept volumes, which represent complete motions, deep neural networks have also been used in motion planning for modeling the SDF of the robot geometry at a given joint configuration. Liu et al. [14] learned a SDF for articulated objects. Their model takes as input a 3D query point and the configuration of the articulated object (robot or human), and outputs the signed distance. They used the model in motion planning for computing repulsive velocities.

Koptev et al. [15] presented a model that, given a joint configuration, computes the minimal distance for each link of a robot to a given 3D query point. They use the gradients of the distances for collision avoidance in their control loop. Li et al. [16] proposed to learn a SDF for each link based on basis functions and ridge regression and compare their approach to deep learning-based methods.

In contrast to Baxter et al. [10], our model is a SDF which can continuously represent the distance function and thereby avoids discretization errors and the computational burden of the network having to output a dense 3D voxel grid. In contrast to Lee et al. [11], our model is conditioned on the motion parameters, and thus the trained network is generally applicable to any motion of the robot. Closest to our implicit swept volume model is the work of Michaux et al. [13]. They use a specific motion type in which the motion is partitioned in one phase with constant acceleration, followed by a second phase with constant deceleration. Their swept volumes are parameterized by the initial configuration, speed, and acceleration of the motion. We allow for arbitrary motions parameterized by their start and goal configuration. Further, we represent the obstacles nonparametrically as point clouds, while they use zonotope approximations for the swept volume and the box obstacles.

III. IMPLICIT SWEEPED VOLUME MODEL

The main idea of our approach is to compute the signed distance of a point in the task space to the swept volume of a robot motion. If the signed distance is positive (or greater than a given safety margin), we would consider this motion as collision-free w.r.t. the given point. To check the robot motion against the complete environment, we represent the environment as a point cloud and check the individual points against the swept volume.

We are thus interested in a function f_d that outputs the signed distance of a given point $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ in the task space to the swept volume $V_S(\mathbf{m}) \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ of a given motion \mathbf{m} :

$$f_d: (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{m}) \mapsto d(\mathbf{x}, V_S(\mathbf{m})), \quad (1)$$

where $d(\mathbf{x}, V)$ is the signed distance of a point \mathbf{x} to the boundary of some volume V . The motion is considered collision-free if $f_d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{m}) > 0$. Here, \mathbf{m} are motion parameters that suffice to uniquely define a concrete motion of a certain motion type, e.g., a linear motion in joint space parameterized by the start and goal configurations of the robot: $\mathbf{m} = (\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{q}_1)$, where \mathbf{q}_0 and $\mathbf{q}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{\text{dof}}$ are joint configurations and dof is the degrees of freedom of the robot. We can denote the motion of the robot in the joint space as

$$c: (\mathbf{m}, s) \mapsto \mathbf{q}_s \quad s \in [0, 1] \quad (2)$$

where the motion is supposed to start at $s = 0$ and end at $s = 1$. If we denote by $V_R(\mathbf{q}_s) \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ the volume in the task space occupied by the robot at the joint configuration \mathbf{q}_s ,

Fig. 2: Network architecture: each blue rectangle represents one of the n_b blocks of the network. The input (green) of the network is fed into each block individually. The gray layers are linearly mapping the input and output dimension of the network to the constant block dimension n_{dim} .

then the swept volume can be defined as

$$V_S(\mathbf{m}) = \bigcup_{s \in [0,1]} V_R(c(\mathbf{m}, s)) \quad (3)$$

$$= \bigcup_{s \in [0,1]} V_R(\mathbf{q}_s). \quad (4)$$

Computing an explicit representation that approximates the swept volume V_S , e.g., as a triangle mesh, and using this representation to compute the signed distance to the point \mathbf{x} would be too slow to be useful in motion planning. We therefore learn an implicit representation of the swept volume as a signed distance field, by training a deep neural network that directly computes the function f_d .

IV. METHOD

In the following, we describe the network architecture, the integration with geometric collision checking, and the generation of training data.

A. Network Architecture

We use a simple, fully connected neural network f_θ with parameters θ to approximate the function f_d of (1). The main component of our network is a block consisting of a sequence of layers. These are a linear layer with constant input and output dimension, a ReLU activation function, and a Batch-Norm layer. We introduce skip connections [17] for each block adding the block input to the block output. The block dimension n_{dim} denotes the input (and output) dimension of its linear layer. Our networks are composed of n_b blocks of equal dimension n_{dim} . These are the two most important hyperparameters of the architecture. Inspired by [18], we further introduce jump connections, concatenating the input of the network to each output of a block. Finally, the blocks are enclosed in an initial linear layer mapping from the input dimension to the block dimension, and a final layer mapping the block dimension to a single scalar value, the predicted signed distance. The architecture of the network is depicted in Fig. 2.

B. Integration with Geometric Collision Checking

We address the problem of finding a collision-free motion in a predefined set of motions $\mathbf{M} = \{\mathbf{m}_j\}_{j=1}^m$. Given a point cloud $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3\}_{i=1}^n$ of the environment and some

motion $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbf{M}$, we are interested in the minimum distance of the point cloud to the swept volume

$$d(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m}) := \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}} d(\mathbf{x}, V_S(\mathbf{m})). \quad (5)$$

To find a collision-free motion in \mathbf{M} , we like to find some $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbf{M}$ satisfying $d(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m}) > \epsilon_S$, where ϵ_S is a safety margin set by the user. Computation of $d(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m})$ for each $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbf{M}$ by a GCC is time-consuming. Therefore, we make use of our neural implicit swept volume model $f_\theta(\cdot, \cdot)$ and compute

$$\hat{d}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m}) := \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}} f_\theta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{m}) \quad (6)$$

as a proxy for $d(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m})$. While this speeds up the distance computation, the resulting estimates are now less reliable. We therefore propose to interleave fast computations $\hat{d}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m})$ with the exact distance computations $d(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m})$ by the following algorithm, which we refer to as (GCC-NN):

Algorithm 1 (GCC-NN)

- 1: **Input:** $\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{X}, \hat{d}(\cdot, \cdot), d(\cdot, \cdot), \epsilon_S$
 - 2: $\mathbf{M}_{\text{done}} \leftarrow \emptyset$
 - 3: **for** $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbf{M}$ **do** ▷ First Loop
 - 4: $\hat{\delta} \leftarrow \hat{d}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m})$
 - 5: **if** $\hat{\delta} > \epsilon_S$ **then**
 - 6: $\delta \leftarrow d(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m})$
 - 7: $\mathbf{M}_{\text{done}} \leftarrow \mathbf{M}_{\text{done}} \cup \mathbf{m}$
 - 8: **if** $\delta > \epsilon_S$ **then**
 - 9: **return** \mathbf{m}, δ
 - 10: Sort $\mathbf{M} \setminus \mathbf{M}_{\text{done}}$ by $\hat{\delta}$ in descending order
 - 11: **for** $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbf{M} \setminus \mathbf{M}_{\text{done}}$ **do** ▷ Second Loop
 - 12: $\delta \leftarrow d(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{m})$
 - 13: **if** $\delta > \epsilon_S$ **then**
 - 14: **return** \mathbf{m}, δ
 - 15: **return** No collision-free motion found
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In a first loop, we run the network for each motion and only invoke the GCC if a signed distance $\hat{\delta}$ greater than the safety margin ϵ_S is predicted. If a collision-free motion is found, the algorithm returns. In case no collision-free motion is detected in the first loop, we resume with all motions which have not yet been processed by the GCC. We sort the remaining motions according to their predicted distances $\hat{\delta}$ in descending order. Then, we run a second loop, where we check each motion with the GCC until a collision-free motion is found or the algorithm returns with no collision-free motion found. We thereby effectively reduce the average number of exact collision checks that need to be executed before finding the first collision-free motion in \mathbf{M} .

C. Dataset Generation

Our training datasets consist of tuples $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{q}_1, \delta)$ with query points \mathbf{x} , the start and goal joint configurations, \mathbf{q}_0 and \mathbf{q}_1 , and the label: the signed distance δ .

Our method is applicable to any type of motion, which can be uniquely defined by \mathbf{q}_0 and \mathbf{q}_1 , since the exact motion is implicitly defined via the training data. Therefore, we will

consider two motion types: a linear joint space motion, and a spline motion in the task space (as used by KUKA Agilus robots). We will call the respective datasets LINEAR and SPLINE.

For a single motion, we first sample \mathbf{q}_0 and \mathbf{q}_1 uniformly from within the individual joint limits. For a linear joint space motion, we discretize this motion into 200 steps by linearly interpolating in joint space between \mathbf{q}_0 and \mathbf{q}_1 . For a spline motion, we use equidistant steps of the flange along the spline in the task space. This yields a varying number of steps per motion, though comparably many as for the linear case. For a given discretized motion, we compute the sequence of poses of each link of the robot. The associated geometries of a link along with their pose sequence is the input for the swept volume algorithm [5] as implemented by the `gpytoolbox` library [19]. This method outputs the swept volume as a triangle mesh. We use an epsilon parameter of 15 mm and otherwise use the default parameters of the library. The swept volumes of the individual link geometries are then merged into a final swept volume by using the Boolean union operation of `libigl` [20].

Note, that the discretization accuracy is thereby determined during data generation, where arbitrary methods for swept volume generation can be used. This only affects the quantity of training data and the time which is necessary to train the models. The inference time of the trained model is therefore mostly independent of the discretization accuracy.

Given the mesh, we sample points in the task space and compute their distances to the mesh. The points are sampled in a such a way, that we have a global coverage of the task space but also pay attention to the boundary of the mesh. For this, we first sample points uniformly in a fixed bounding box large enough to cover any motion of the robot. We use a density of 0.25 points per dm^3 . Next we sample points on the surface of the swept volume, using a density of 0.2 points per cm^2 . For each such surface point we additionally sample 2 points from a spherical Gaussian distribution centered at this point (with $\sigma = 3$ mm). To further cover the space inside the volume, we sample for each surface point a second surface point at random, and define the point’s location by uniformly sampling from the line connecting these points.

V. EXPERIMENTS

We validate our approach in three different experiments. First, we investigate the accuracy of the signed distance prediction of the neural networks. We then evaluate Alg. 1 in an artificial path planning scenario as well as a real-world bin picking application.

If not otherwise stated, we use an KUKA Agilus KR 6 with 6 degrees of freedom. Computations are done with an Nvidia GeForce RTX 3090 GPU. We use the Flexible Collision Library (FCL) [21] as the GCC in all our experiments. For training neural networks, we use the Adam optimizer of PyTorch with default parameters $\text{lr} = 0.001$ and $\text{betas} = (0.9, 0.999)$. We use the ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler with factor 0.1 and patience 10 and train the model for 200 epochs. A search over these parameters did not yield any

Fig. 3: Exemplary comparison of different model sizes for the linear joint space motion already shown in Fig. 1. There is a noticeable degradation when going from (c) 11x512 to (d) 5x512, while the difference between (c) 11x512 and (b) 11x1024 is less pronounced. This qualitative finding is also reflected in the metrics shown in Table I.

improvements. For testing, we choose the checkpoint with the best loss on the validation set. Before inference, we export the PyTorch models to TorchScript programs. Source code and checkpoints for the models, as well as the dataset LINEAR are available online [22].

A. Implicit Swept Volume Modeling

In the first experiment, we test the accuracy of the signed distance prediction on the two datasets LINEAR and SPLINE introduced in Section IV-C. For each dataset we generated 20 000 motions and sampled approximately 4 500 points per motion. We use 60 % of the data for training, 25 % for validation, and 15 % for testing. The mean absolute errors (MAE) on the test sets are reported in Table I. We investigate three different network architectures 5x512, 11x512, and 11x1024, varying in their number of blocks n_b (5 or 11) and their block dimension n_{dim} (512 or 1024). The MAE of the prediction for both linear and spline motions is below 4.5 mm in all cases. For both datasets, we can improve the error to below 3.5 mm by using 11 instead of 5 blocks and approximately 3.1 mm by increasing the block dimension from 512 to 1024. To further illustrate the prediction quality of the networks, we used the marching cubes algorithm to reconstruct the swept volume meshes from the networks (with a resolution of 1 cm). Fig. 3 shows a comparison of different model sizes. More reconstructions for linear and spline motions are shown in Fig. 4.

We further report the inference times of our networks. Table II shows average computation times for processing three different sizes of point batches. The first two batch sizes represent the point cloud sizes from the box world and bin picking experiments, that we detail later. The inference times approximately represent the time necessary to check one motion for collision in these scenarios. We add a batch size of 20 000 to observe how inference times scale for larger inputs. We also trained a 16 bit precision variant of

Fig. 4: Comparison between the ground truth swept volume meshes (gray) and meshes reconstructed from the neural networks (red) via the marching cubes algorithm (resolution: 1 cm). The upper row shows linear joint space motions, while the lower row shows spline motions. For both rows, 11x1024 models were used to predict the signed distances. The motions are the first four motions of their respective test sets, and thus have not been used in training.

the smallest model to further speed up inference times. As our unit of measurement is millimeter, this has no effect on the accuracy of the model and approximately halves the computation time for larger batch sizes. For the two smaller batch sizes of the path planning experiments, we observe that collision checks can be performed in under a millisecond.

B. Box World Collision Checking

In the following experiment, we evaluate Alg. 1 for motion planning in artificially generated box world scenes as seen in Fig. 5. Each of the 100 scenes contains 50 boxes with a random orientation and a location sampled uniformly at random from within a volume defined by $x, y \in [-1 \text{ m}, 1 \text{ m}]$ and $z \in [0 \text{ m}, 1.5 \text{ m}]$. The side lengths of each box are independently sampled uniformly from the interval [1 cm, 10 cm] (the robot base is centered at the origin). For each scene, we sample a single start configuration uniformly from within the joint limits, and 100 random goal configurations, which yields 10 000 motions in total. On average, 25.2% of the motions are collision-free. The minimum number of collision-free motions in a scene is 0, the maximum is 66. For the neural network, we represent this environment as a point cloud by sampling points from the surface of the boxes with a density of 0.1 points per cm^2 . In the box world, the GCC reports the signed distance of the robot model to the boxes represented as triangle meshes. For this, the linear joint space motion is discretized into 200 steps and each configuration is checked. We apply the LINEAR 5x512 16bit model to predict signed distances. Using a safety margin of 5 mm to classify signed distances into collisions and non-collisions, the network achieves a classification accuracy of 93.1%, with 6.3% false positives, and 0.6% false negatives.

We compare two algorithms for finding the first collision-free path of each scene. The first method (GCC₀) applies the

TABLE I: Depicted are the mean absolute errors of the predicted signed distances. Results are provided for different model architectures and the two datasets.

	Mean Absolute Error (mm)	
	LINEAR	SPLINE
5x512	4.38 ±5.67	4.32 ±5.55
11x512	3.45 ±4.71	3.32 ±4.49
11x1024	3.08 ±4.27	3.11 ±4.28

TABLE II: Inference times for different models and input sizes. We report the time necessary to process a batch of 1000, 3000 or 20 000 points. The first two rows represent the point cloud sizes used in the path planning experiments Box World and Bin Picking. The standard deviation of the computation times is in the range of micro seconds and therefore omitted.

	Inferences times (ms)		
	Box World	Bin Picking	
	1000 Points	3000 Points	20000 Points
11x1024	2.17	5.55	33.10
11x512	0.91	2.17	11.20
5x512	0.50	1.08	5.42
5x512 16bit	0.49	0.70	2.63

GCC on each motion in the given order. The second method (GCC-NN) represents Alg. 1 using the neural network as a proxy. As timing depends on the order in which the motions of each scene are checked, we average over 1000 permutations for each scene, which yields 100 000 timing samples. The results shown in Table III indicate a speed-up of 49% from 269 ms (GCC₀) to 136 ms (GCC-NN) for the average time to find a collision-free path. Due to the pre-checks done by the network, the average number of exact collision checks done by the GCC is reduced to less than a third, with 2.0 exact checks per scene in (GCC-NN).

C. Bin Picking Collision Checking

Finally, we investigate collision checking in a real-world bin picking application. Fig. 6 depicts a KUKA Agilus KR 10 (with attached gripper) grasping gearbox housings out of a bin.

Fig. 5: An example of a box world scene, with randomly sampled boxes and points on the surface of the boxes.

Fig. 6: Bin picking application using the KUKA.SmartBinPicking software. The image on the left displays a test scenario with 40 gearbox housings. The right image shows detected objects with collision-free endeffector paths (green) and objects without collision-free paths (red).

We use the KUKA.SmartBinPicking software to produce multiple grasp candidates for a given scene. A given grasp $\mathbf{q}_{\text{grasp}}$ is reached by two splines $\mathbf{q}_{\text{start}} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}_{\text{inVia}}$ and $\mathbf{q}_{\text{inVia}} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}_{\text{grasp}}$, where $\mathbf{q}_{\text{start}}$ is the starting configuration above the bin, and $\mathbf{q}_{\text{inVia}}$ is a via point located close to the target object, which is introduced to increase the chance for collision-free paths. Once the object has been grasped, it is moved out of the bin using two similar splines: $\mathbf{q}_{\text{grasp}} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}_{\text{outVia}}$ and $\mathbf{q}_{\text{outVia}} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}_{\text{end}}$, where $\mathbf{q}_{\text{end}} \neq \mathbf{q}_{\text{start}}$ is the final configuration above the bin, and $\mathbf{q}_{\text{outVia}} \neq \mathbf{q}_{\text{inVia}}$ is another via point. We refer to the sequential execution of the first two splines as \mathbf{m}_{in} , and the other two splines as \mathbf{m}_{out} . The GCC checks each of the motions \mathbf{m}_{in} and \mathbf{m}_{out} in one pass, while the NN model is called twice (once for each spline). For evaluating our approach, we collected 22 real-world scenes (see Fig. 6) with 15 to 40 gearbox housings in the bin. Grasp sampling of the system yielded 35 ± 7 possible grasp poses per scene where $82 \pm 39\%$ of the motions \mathbf{m}_{in} to grasp candidates and $81 \pm 39\%$ of motions \mathbf{m}_{out} out of the box resulted in collisions. A 5×512 16bit model is trained for the new robot with attached gripper using the same data generation process as described in Section V-A. While the network was trained with the detailed model of the robot, the GCC uses a convexified robot model for collision checking to speed up collision checks.

Bin picking requires to precisely predict distances where the robot geometry is close to the point cloud. This inherent difficulty provides an interesting scenario, where the neural network is not able to detect collision-free paths anymore for

TABLE III: Results of the box world experiment. (GCC-NN) halves the total time for collision checking of (GCC₀) by using three times less exact collision checks.

Results Box World Experiment		
	(GCC ₀)	(GCC-NN)
total time (ms)	269 ±286	136 ±68
# Exact checks	6.69 ±11.98	2.00 ±9.85
# NN checks		14.05 ±24.20

TABLE IV: Results of the bin picking experiment: Performance of (GCC₀) and (GCC-NN) is shown for motions into the bin in columns 2 and 3 and motions out of the bin in columns 4 and 5. It can be seen, that (GCC-NN) improves the total time for collision checking by 25% and 30%, respectively, using less exact collision checks than (GCC₀).

	\mathbf{m}_{in} (into bin)		\mathbf{m}_{out} (out of bin)	
	(GCC ₀)	(GCC-NN)	(GCC ₀)	(GCC-NN)
total time (ms)	190 ±215	143 ±188	194 ±223	135 ±185
# Exact checks	6.90 ±8.30	3.38 ±7.32	7.2 ±8.7	3.25 ±7.3
# NN checks		70.5 ±13.00		70.5 ±13.0

the given safety margin. Alg. 1 is therefore reduced to the second loop: the minimum signed distances of all possible motions are predicted by the network in advance, and all motions are then checked by the GCC in descending order of their predicted signed distance.

As can be seen, (GCC-NN) can still improve the total time, if the quality of the signed distance prediction is high enough to sort motions favorably. Table IV shows that the number of collision checks is reduced by approximately 50% compared to (GCC₀) for motions into and out of the bin. The average time for checking a given motion is 28 ± 4 ms for the GCC and 0.70 ms for the network. Thereby (GCC-NN) achieves a speed-up of 25% and 30% in total time consumption over the (GCC₀). To produce the results, we again sampled 1000 permutations for the order in which the motions are checked.

VI. CONCLUSION

We proposed a novel approach for neural implicit swept volumes, parameterized by the start and goal configuration. We further introduced an algorithm for interleaving these implicit models with geometric collision checking. In our experiments, we achieve accurate neural representations of swept volumes and show, that we can significantly speed up a real-world bin picking application with our algorithm.

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